

Comparison of natural dried eucalyptus wood fiber morphology in different conditions

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Abstract

The wood material gain or lose moisture from the air based upon the conditions of the surrounding environment because of its hygroscopic structure. For this reason, it is an important issue that it must be dried to required moisture level of end use place to prevent deformations (warping, twisting, throughability etc.) formed in the place of use and reduces the dimensional changes. Effects of natural drying conditions on the eucalyptus (*Eucalyptus camaldulensis*) wood fiber morphologies were investigated. For this purpose, eucalyptus timber was dried until air-dried moisture level (12%) by natural drying method in two different conditions (indoor and outdoor) in the Eastern Mediterranean climate conditions. According to the obtained results, the fiber morphologies of woods dried in the indoor were found to be higher than woods dried in the outdoor.

Keywords: Natural drying, fiber morphology, eucalyptus

Farklı ortamlarda doğal kurutulan okaliptüs odununun lif morfolojisinin karşılaştırılması

Özet

Ağaç malzeme, higroskopik yapısı nedeniyle çevresi ile sürekli rutubet alışverişi içerisinde bulunur. Bu özelliği nedeni ile kullanım yerinde oluşabilecek çeşitli deformasyonları (çarpılma, burulma, oluklaşma vb.) önlemek ve boyutsal değişimi en aza indirmek için son kullanım yerinin gerektirdiği rutubet derecesine kadar kurutulması önemli bir husustur. Bu çalışmada; iki farklı ortamda doğal olarak kurutulan okaliptüs (*Eucalyptus camaldulensis*) kerestelerinin lif morfolojisi üzerine ortam farklılığının etkisi araştırılmıştır. Bu amaçla, okaliptüs kerestesi iki farklı ortamda (açık ve kapalı) doğal kurutma yöntemi ile Doğu Akdeniz iklim şartlarında hava kuru rutubet derecesine (%12) kadar kurutulmuştur. Kurutulan kerestelerden hazırlanan test örnekleri üzerinde yapılan ölçümler sonucu, kapalı ortam şartlarında kurutulan okaliptüs kerestesinde lif boyutlarının açık hava şartlarında kurutulanlara göre daha yüksek olduğu belirlenmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Doğal kurutma, lif morfolojisi, okaliptüs

INTRODUCTION

Because of differences in moisture content, eucalyptus is not considered partly a stable wood. The growth stresses caused by the compression inner part of the tree and tension stress on the outer part could generate bend and split in timber. As it dries, eucalyptus tends to shrink more than other

wood species, and may warp. However, if it can be heavily treated with preservatives drying conditions, it might be suitable for wood products (Kilic Ak, 2016).

Wood drying is an important issue for forest products industry. Wood is a material which has various usage areas such as parquet, furniture, paper, composites etc. It has many advantages and disadvantages comparing to other materials. One of the most important disadvantage is that hygroscopic properties this means that wood is gain or lose moisture from the air based upon the conditions of the surrounding environment (Time, 1998). Drying process is an important issue to eliminate these defects. Generally, two main drying methods have been used in Turkey: Kiln-Dry and Air-Dry. Kiln-dry (technical drying) is essentially a well-insulated chamber in which temperature, relative humidity, and air circulation can be controlled, maintained, and readily changed and kiln-dried lumber is often used for wood products (Bousquet, 2000; Salas and Moya, 2014). The air drying of lumber involves exposing piles of stickered lumber to the outdoor air and air-dried lumber is often used in patio furniture, fencing, and decking. The cost of kiln drying is very expensive, so lumber manufacturers use the natural sunlight and wind to start the drying process. Air-drying time vary widely from o couple of weeks to several months depending on species, local weather conditions and time of the year when the material is stacked. Rainfall, temperature, radiation, and relative humidity all affect to drying process (Bown and Lasserre, 2015).

The properties of fibers can be well understood if their physical properties such as length, diameter and cell wall thickness were considered. It refers to these properties as the morphological properties of the fibers. Fiber morphology varies according to the age of the tree, its genus, growth conditions and climate (Kirci, 2000; Istek et al., (2009) . It is an important parameter in determining the suitability of wood raw materials for pulp and paper production. Fiber morphology is also important for other wood products such as wood plastic composites (WPC), solid wood strength as well as fiber and particle boards. A high aspect ratio (fiber length/fiber width) is very important in fiber reinforced composites, as it indicates potential strength properties (Rowell et al., 2000). A study undertaken by Stark and Rowlands concluded that rather than particle size, aspect ratio had the greatest effect on strength and stiffness of WPC. Besides, it has effects on the strength properties of the fiberboard.

The main aim of this study is to determine differences between indoor and outdoor air drying conditions on wood fiber morphology. The specific objective is to measure fiber length, fiber width, cell wall thickness, and lumen diameter of eucalyptus wood fibers and to discuss in terms of wood products properties.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material

Freshly sawn eucalyptus from south of Turkey was used for the experiment. Eucalyptus trees were supplied from Mersin-Karabucak Forest Sub-district Directorate. The raw material was cut into as timbers with dimensions 6x15x300 cm.

Drying Experiment

As a drying method, natural drying technique under the conditions of Kahramanmaraş province located in Mediterranean Region was preferred. Timbers were stacked into two different conditions: Indoor (ID) and outdoor (OD). Drying process was began in summer period (effective drying) on June and followed during one year. For outdoor-drying, climatic factors effecting drying such as temperature, relative humidity, precipitation and wind velocity were supplied momentarily from the meteorological station. Except for precipitation and wind velocity respective values for indoor-drying were measured by Geratech DT-172.

Fiber Morphology

Timbers were chosen to represent all stack and three pieces of 2 cm cubic samples were taken from the center of the body, 15 cm above the root, and 15 cm below the top for determining the fiber morphology. The fiber lengths and widths, lumen diameters, and cell wall thicknesses from the morphologic properties of the raw materials were measured with a microscope. To measure the fiber

morphologic properties of the specimens (0.5-mm thickness and 2-cm long, parallel to the fiber), the chloride method was performed (Wise and Karl, 1962). In this method, specimens were immersed into chloride solution until they were defibered. Fiber dimension variables were measured using Olympus BX51 microscope with a 10X ocular lens provided with a measuring scale. Fiber width and lumen diameter were measured with a magnification of 40X object lens and the fiber length was measured with a magnification of 10X object lens. Mean values were calculated from the measurement of 80 fibers in each plant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stacked eucalyptus timbers were dried in ID and OD conditions during a year. The relative humidity and temperature, important parameters in the drying process, were measured throughout the year and are given in Table 1 as seasonal. At the end of the effective drying period (summer), moisture content of ID and OD were 12% and 9.8% whereas after one year, respective values were 13.3% and 14.5%, respectively. In addition, the average annual rainfall and wind velocity values that are effective on OD are 2.70 mm and 2.10 m/sec, respectively.

Table 12. Seasonal temperature and relative humidity values in Kahramanmaras

Drying Conditions	Drying/climatic Factors	Summer	Autumn	Winter	Spring	Average Values
ID	Temperature °C	26.4	20.6	10.3	18.1	19
	Relative Humidity %	63.2	54.9	58.3	55.6	58
OD	Temperature °C	31.3	22.3	8.1	18.5	20
	Relative Humidity %	32.5	40.2	56.7	44.2	43

The fiber length, fiber width, lumen diameter, and cell wall thickness of eucalyptus dried indoor conditions were found to be 0.830 mm, 14.99 μm , 7.19 μm , and 3.98 μm , respectively. The respective values for outdoor conditions were 0.752 mm, 14.43 μm , 7.33 μm , and 3.56 μm , respectively. According to that, the fiber dimensions of eucalyptus dried ID condition were greater than those of dried OD. T-test analysis was executed to the measured values and obtained data were shown in Table 2.

When Table 2 were evaluated considering Table 1 given in drying factors, it can be said that the fiber sizes of the timbers that is dried in OD with high relative humidity and high temperature, lose more water and reduce in size more. T-test analysis of the fiber wall thickness and fiber lengths reveals significant differences in terms of indoor and outdoor drying environments. This is stemmed from differences in temperature and relative humidity values.

Table 13. The fiber morphology of eucalyptus woods dried two different conditions

Fiber Dimensions	Drying Conditions	N	Mean	Standard deviation	Standard error	COV	t _{value}	Sig. (2-tailed)
Fiber length (mm)	ID	80	830.56	139.62	18.493	16.81	-3.127	0.002
	OD		752.40	127.26	16.856	16.91		
Fiber width (μm)	ID	80	14.99	3.38	0.383	22.54	-0.906	0.367
	OD		14.43	4.24	0.480	29.38		
Cell wall thickness (μm)	ID	80	3.98	1.12	0.120	28.14	-2.882	0.004
	OD		3.56	0.79	0.085	22.19		
Lumen diameter (μm)	ID	80	7.19	1.26	0.143	17.52	0.407	0.685
	OD		7.33	2.60	0.294	35.47		

*COV: Coefficient of Variation

As is known, drying is a case related to the movement of the hygroscopic water (absorption-desorption). For this reason, removing free and bound water from wood is desirable. As shown in Table 1, while in effective drying period the temperature and relative humidity of outdoor were 31.3°C and 32.5%, in indoor they were 26.4°C and 63.2%, respectively. Considering these data, it can be said that a more protective drying has taken place in ID environment. In Table 2, the analysis results also confirm this. This is indicative of significant differences between ID and OD lumen diameters. Due to

the lumen diameter, there are also differences between in the fiber widths. When water begins to leave the cell walls at 25 to 30 percent moisture content, the cell walls begin to shrink (Reeb, 1995). In this study, the cell wall thickness of the OD was shrink more than ID due to rapidly drying.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the fiber morphology of eucalyptus timbers' dried two different conditions were determined and fiber length, fiber width, cell wall thickness as well as lumen diameter were measured to determine differences. The conclusions obtained from this study were given below:

4. During drying process, the OD temperature was measured higher than ID temperature whereas the relative humidity of OD was found to be lower. For this reasons, it can be said that drying eucalyptus timbers in indoor gives more suitable results.
5. Drying in OD was occurred rapidly due to the higher temperature and lower relative humidity. At the end of the effective drying period, the moisture content of the timber dried in OD and ID were measured 9.8% and 12%, respectively. The respective values at the end of the drying process were found 14.5% and 13.3%.
6. Due to variations in the temperature and relative humidity, in the fiber morphological properties of eucalyptus timber dried in two different conditions significant differences have been identified. According to the obtained data, it has been determined that there are significant differences in the fiber lengths, fiber widths and cell wall thicknesses of the timbers dried in ID and OD, whereas non-significant differences in the lumen diameters.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by KSU-BAP (The Scientific Research Projects Unit of Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University) No. 2017/4-48 UKSP.

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